

Impact of Geometric Variation on the Performance of Cold Formed Bearings

*J. Woodhead, J. D. Booker, C. E. Truman
Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bristol, UK.*

Keywords: Cold forming, geometrical/dimensional features, process capability analysis, finite element analysis, robust design.

Abstract

Plain spherical bearings are precision assemblies with a low frictional moment finding wide application in industry where they operate in harsh environments. They are manufactured using a cold forming process known as 'nosing'. An experiential approach is currently used by a manufacturer to develop new bearings and determine associated process settings. Typically, inefficiencies can be observed for the bearing assembly post-nosing where any one of nine different failure modes may occur leading to rework or scrap costs due to a number of component and process inconsistencies. The initial focus is the outer bearing shell component and the geometrical relationships of the end chamfer features. Process capability measures are developed for a bearing model, with parts individually tracked through the nosing process to examine the influence out-of-tolerance variation on process integrity, measured forming loads and frictional moment. A validated Finite Element (FE) model is used to predict the complex elastic-plastic material behaviour at high strain-rates in the nosing process to support the simulation of in-process failure modes. These models take into account the geometrical and dimensional variations of the chamfers, material property variation and coefficient of friction. Predictions are made for feature process capabilities which produce lower failure rates in production.

1. Introduction

The applications of the plain spherical bearing are wide and varied, including within the aerospace, locomotive, automotive and food industries. Figure 1a) shows a schematic of a plain spherical bearing indicating three common components: a central inner race which enables the bearing to be axially supported; an outer sleeve provides a platform for other components in the assembly and a composite liner in between the inner and outer races, affixed to the latter, provides self-lubrication and frictional properties during operation. Figure 1b) shows a typical bearing in a locomotive application. Nosing is the cold-metal forming process primarily used in the manufacture of plain spherical bearings (Orsolini & Booker, 2012; Woodhead & Booker, 2013). In this process the outer race is formed on each side simultaneously whereby it is placed, together with the inner race and composite liner, in between two identical spherical dies as shown in Figure 2a). The upper die displaces along the bearings axis, and the bearing is subjected to compression at the contact interface between the die and the outer race as the

DOI:10.4122/dtu:2103

Reviewed by: *Thomas J. Howard*
Tobias Eifler

Cited as: Woodhead, J., Booker, J. D. and Truman, C. E., 2014. Impact of Geometric Variation on the Performance of Cold Formed Bearings. In: Howard, T. J. and Eifler, T., ed. 2014. *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Robust Design - ISoRD14*. Copenhagen, Denmark. pp. 159-170.

force is translated axially. This causes the outer race to undergo elastic-plastic deformation, until it geometrically conforms to the shape of the inner race, Figure 2b). Custom-made press machines are used to produce the level of force required, up to several hundred Metric Tons.

Figure 1. Plain spherical bearing; (a) CAD cut-away view (final bearing product, after the nosing process and additional machining of the outer race has been completed), (b) example application (rail locomotion)

Figure 2. Schematic of the nosing operation (a) start and (b) end of the stroke

Undesirable failures can occur during the nosing process, resulting in either extensive re-working or scrapping if the correct geometric conformity or target frictional moment cannot be achieved. Nosing is a complex process, with the root cause of a process failure being an interaction of many factors (Antony, 2003). Incorrect pressure, displacement, number of cycles (i.e. the number of consecutive times the press will lower), machine specifications and pre-form design are just a few contributing factors, and can produce any combination of the failure modes identified in Figure 3. The failure modes were discussed with company machine operators (with a combined experience of over 40 years), as part of an ongoing project to generate scientific and engineering knowledge to be used in future product developments. Using this experience, a system of weightings (roughly following an FMEA approach) was developed to produce an overall risk score (Figure 3), based upon the complexity of the various causes, the production impact and the frequency of occurrence. The system diagram in Figure 4 outlines key factors/variables which may influence the nosing process.

Figure 3. Nosing failure modes, their relative occurrence and impact upon production

Figure 4. System diagram showing inputs, controllable/uncontrollable variables and outputs

Process failure causes commonly attributed to the most prevalent failure modes are unequal geometry on the outer race of the bearing and variations in tooling set-up. Variations in press tooling and any inherent variability in the machine itself are difficult to control and challenging to model. However, the geometric features of the bearing can be controlled, specifically the chamfers, which are initially set by the design engineers and subsequently machined within the business. The chamfers are the first point of contact with the die, and this initial contact plays an important role in influencing the nosing process, as they promote easier formability of the component in order to achieve a greater geometric conformity between the outer and inner race. The chamfer length of the investigated component is $1.315 \text{ mm} \pm 0.142 \text{ mm}$ by $15^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ on the outer race (Figure 5). Tolerances are usually set based on:

- **Waste reduction:** The least volume of material required to produce the final design specified by the customer;
- **Cost effectiveness:** If sleeve dimensions that fit an existing die set also maintain compatibility with the customer specifications;
- **Performance:** The sleeve needs to accommodate enough liner to produce the required frictional moment at the correct geometric conformity;
- **Compatibility:** The sleeve needs to be compatible with existing tooling i.e. sleeve inner diameter small enough to fit press machine location pin, sleeve length short enough to stay within die set without protruding into the bore.

Figure 5. Baseline bearing model outer race, with section view indicating key geometric features with tolerances (dimensions in mm), and isometric views indicating the measurement points (a) on either side of the bearing, (b) between bearing sides

If tolerances are exceeded the company know that, through experience, the risk of certain failure modes occurring increases i.e. too long a sleeve length leads to ‘necking’, too large a sleeve outer diameter leads to ‘saturnisation’, too small a sleeve inner diameter leads to ‘liner slippage’ etc. Some feature dimensions on the bearing outer race will be manufactured to a minimum and others to a maximum. Should any features fall within this 97th percentile of the statistical distribution, it is not known exactly what effect this would have either during the nosing process or on the final output. However, a 2-factor/2-level DoE on the angle and length of the bearing chamfers using FE simulations shows a correlation between these two key dimensions (Figure 6). Furthermore, no geometric tolerances are specified on engineering drawings, leading to the statistical possibility that the opposing sides of the bearing outer race may have minimum and maximum extreme values respectively (e.g. one side having a minimum chamfer angle and the other having a maximum). Empirical evidence suggests this may contribute to any number of failure modes, in particular ‘offset’ and ‘tipping’, contributing also to ‘liner slippage’.

Figure 6. Combined effect of minimum/maximum chamfer angle and length on forming vload

2. Methodology

2.1 Objectives

The objective of this study is to ascertain the batch variation of geometric features of a high-volume production bearing model, in order to understand the impact upon the measureable process outputs of forming load and frictional moment. This knowledge is used to enable new, more robust, geometrical tolerances to be set. The stages involved and presented are;

- Measure bearing outer race dimensions (i.e. chamfer outer and inner diameter, angle and geometric length) prior to the nosing process;
- Record nosing process outputs (i.e. forming load and frictional moment) of all measured bearing samples;
- Statistically analyse the data to access whether there is a statistical significance between the key features of either side of the bearing outer race;
- Calculate process capability indices, and provide recommendations as to process performance.

2.2 Measurements

The measurements were taken using a high precision optical comparator (Figure 7) with accuracy in the order of $\pm 10^{-6}$ m. The bearing was mounted on a V-block with a 360° turn-table in order that the bearing could be rotated to measure the both sides with minimal handling. Lights on the machine can be directed at close range toward the sample to project an image onto the screen. A green light is used to project the shadow of the bearing onto the screen for precise measurement of edges, and a white light can be used to view any detail on the bear-

ing surface. Mechanical levers operate the 4-axis table to position the point of interest on the viewing screen. The x, y, z coordinates relating to the cross-hairs in the centre of the screen were recorded from the digital display. Each bearing sample was marked every 45° of each side, to indicate where to take measurements around the circumference. The detail view was used to measure the chamfer inner diameter, whereas the shadow view was used to measure the chamfer outer diameter, geometric chamfer length (the true length of the chamfer from edge-to-edge) and the chamfer angle. Both inner and outer diameters were measured on one side, the bearing was rotated 180°, and the process repeated. The bearing was then placed onto a V-block with the flat sides normal to the table surface, in order that the chamfer length and angle could be measured on both sides.

Figure 7. Optical comparator with bearing outer race in-situ, showing; lens and lights directed at the part mounted on the 4-axis table (left), and shadow-view of the bearing outer race (right)

A CAD program was used to calculate the offset in concentricity between the outer and inner diameter of the chamfer. This was due to the number of points measured, as well as providing a convenient method of visualising the results. The recorded x, y co-ordinates were imported into the software in order that the centre point of both the inner and outer diameters was calculated accurately, and the total shift between each side of the bearing (geometric eccentricity) could also be measured.

2.3 Analysis Tools

Statistical analysis is performed on the bearing outer race, and the data provides an indication as to the extent of variation in the key features of the bearing outer race. The process is under statistical control; hence, Normal distributions are assumed and parameters are determined using the linear rectification method (Booker et al., 2001), except for concentricity. For features which have negative values such as those with a target value of zero (zero-bound data), or data that is recorded as absolute deviations from a target value, additional statistical processing is required. Concentricity is a truly zero-bound form of feature data; therefore, once the distribution is plotted, one tail of the distribution is negative. Although this is mathematically correct, in reality there are no negative values allowed, and the normal density function must be 'folded' (Kotz & Lovelace, 1998) at zero. The folded standard normal distribution (equation 1), the population mean (equation 2) and the standard deviation (equation 3), are then calculated as follows:

$$f_1(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(x-\mu)^2}{\sigma} \right) + \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(x-\mu)^2}{\sigma} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_{f_1} = E(X) = \mu \left[1 - 2\Phi \left(-\frac{\mu}{\sigma} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mu/\sigma)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{f_1}^2 = E \left[(X - \mu_{f_1})^2 \right] = \sigma^2 + \mu^2 + \mu_{f_1}^2 \quad (3)$$

Where σ is the normal standard deviation, μ is the normal population mean, X is the variable of interest and Φ is a function of the standard normal distribution. Using the statistical data, a process capability analysis is then performed, which will indicate current process performance using C_p/C_{pk} .

2.4 Part Details

The key features and dimensions of the component to be measured are detailed in Figure 5. The outer bearing race material properties, determined previously via uniaxial compression testing to ASTM standards (Woodhead & Booker, 2013), are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of bearing outer race

Property	Symbol	Value
0.2% Proof Stress	σ_y	1.080 [GPa]
Poisson's Ratio	ν	0.33
Young's Modulus of Elasticity	E	199.80 [GPa]
Strength Coefficient	K	1.750 [GPa]
Strain-hardening Exponent	n	0.13

3. Results from In-process Tracking

3.1 Geometric Variation

3.1.1 Concentricity

Chamfer centre-points on either side of the bearings are shifted away from one another at various different angles (Figure 8). Some shifts between sides can be in the same direction or opposed to one another, and this difference between the centre-points of each side is the geometric concentricity. The type of shift between the two sides will affect how contact between the chamfer and die initiates, potentially having a significant effect on the remainder of the nosing operation; therefore, a more significant factor during the nosing process may not simply be the individual shift in chamfer concentricity, but rather the geometric concentricity (offset in concentricity between either side). Throughout the following figures, samples 2 and 14 from this batch of bearing outer races have been highlighted as samples of interest. The mean offset in concentricity (for both sides of the bearings together), is 0.01mm which is within the general tolerance limit of 0.0635mm. Larger distributions were calculated for the offset in geometric concentricity, resulting in a population mean of 0.05mm which, while still being within the tolerance limit, is very close. Furthermore, in terms of geometric concentricity, 3 standard deviations is more than a 0.2mm shift. If a bearing were to have an offset in geometric concentricity within the extreme tail-end of this distribution, it may contribute to one or more of the failure modes highlighted in Figure 3. The population means for concentricity are almost identical on either side of the bearing outer race. Both distributions correlate well, with the distribution range of side 2 being slightly larger than that of side 1. The tail-end of the distribution exceeds the upper tolerance by approximately 0.02mm; however, less than 2% of the total distribution is outside tolerance. The concentricity data appears well behaved, but a further analysis of the geometric concentricity, once the negative part of the data is folded back, reveals a large standard deviation of over 0.2mm. Up to 3 standard deviations is approximately 0.6mm, resulting in over 60% of the distribution being outside tolerance. The disparity between concentricity and geometric concentricity can be seen Figure 9.

Figure 8. Cartesian coordinates of chamfer centre-points for both sides of the bearing sleeve (origin of the represents the sleeve outer diameter centre, tolerance limits = $\pm 0.0635\text{mm}$)

Figure 9. Folded normal distributions (Ndf) for; (left) shift in chamfer concentricity (target mean 0mm), and (right) shift in geometric chamfer concentricity (tolerance limit $0 \pm 0.0635\text{mm}$)

3.1.2 Angle

The population means for the angle of the chamfers between sides 1 and 2 of the bearing outer races are similar, to within two decimal places, indicating high precision. The process capability, C_p , index is acceptable, indicating that the process is capable, but the chamfer angle tolerance is large ($\pm 2^\circ$) and therefore the process capability index will be high, as even 2 standard deviations of the SND curve is well within the tolerance limits. The distribution is not perfectly centred though, and is shifted towards the lower specification limit (Figure 10 – left); however, this is within 1.5 standard deviations which is a normal shift for any process (Booker et al., 2001). The tail-end of the distributions for both side 1 and 2 is less than 1% outside the lower specification limit (LSL), but this results in the C_{pk} index being reduced to 1.0, indicating that the process is not capable. Further analysis was conducted firstly, on the difference between the angles opposite each other on the same side of the bearing, and then secondly, on the difference between the angles opposite each other on different sides of the bearing (Figure 10). This transforms the data into zero-bound data, similar to concentricity, because the target value is zero degrees (i.e. no difference in chamfer angles between measurement points), therefore; a folded normal density function (equation 1) was calculated to remove any negative data, as before. Analysis indicated that the mean difference in chamfer angle between sides 1 and 2 shows the largest shift at almost 0.6° .

Figure 10. Standard normal distributions (SND) and folded (Ndf) for; (left) chamfer angle for sides 1 and 2 (target mean 15°), and (right) difference in chamfer angle between sides 1 and 2

3.1.3 Length

The population means, μ , of side 1 and 2 are shifted towards the lower specification limit, and side 1 even falls fractionally outside tolerance (Figure 11 – left). Further analysis was again conducted firstly, on the difference between the lengths opposite each other on the same side of the bearing, and then secondly, on the difference between the lengths opposite each other on different sides of the bearing (Figure 11 – right). Once again, this transforms the data into zero-bound data, similar to concentricity, because the target value is zero millimetres (i.e. no difference in chamfer lengths between measurement points); therefore, a folded normal density function (equation 1) was calculated to remove any negative data within the normal distribution. Analysis indicated that distributions for both sides 1 and 2 for the difference between chamfer lengths both fell within tolerance (data not provided here), and had high Cpk indices, however; the population mean, μ , for the difference in chamfer lengths between sides is 0.15mm, placing it outside tolerance with less than 25% of the distribution within tolerance (Figure 11 – right). This indicates that there is a manufacturing issue in producing this feature, and a more detailed analysis revealed that the de-burring process caused an excessive amount of material to be removed from the chamfer on Side 1.

Figure 11. Standard normal distributions (SND) for; (left) chamfer length, for sides 1 and 2 (target mean 1.315mm), and (right) difference in chamfer length between sides 1 and 2

3.1.4 Inner Diameter

There was not predicted to be any large variation in measured values for the inner diameter of the outer race, but the measurements were taken for completeness. The statistical analysis confirms that the population mean, μ , is within tolerance, with a low standard deviation, giving this variable a high Cp index. Furthermore, the mean is almost exactly midway between specification limits, with the SND curve spanning less than 15% of the range between them. Hence the Cpk index is 8, indicating that this dimension may be expensive to produce and production machines utilised are not optimum.

3.2 Volumetric Variation

On further analysis, the volume of each bearing sample was calculated, and the results were analysed statistically (Figure 12). The company do not specify tolerances for the volume of parts, but theoretical limits were calculated based upon the combination of geometrical tolerances that are specified on the engineering drawing for this component. Sample number 14 was recorded as having consistently one of the highest forming loads, highest frictional moments and largest volumes; whereas, sample number 2 was recorded as having consistently one of the lowest forming loads, lowest frictional moments and lowest volumes. The larger the volume, the greater the energy required to produce the same amount of deformation, consistent with metal forming theory (Caminaga & Gentile, 2005). Additional factors such as contact between dies and bearing surface and lubrication used, and adverse shear stresses (Woodhead et al., 2014), all increase the amount of energy required to complete an operation resulting in higher local pressures and temperature rises. These factors together with the repeated impact of the dies and the sliding of the bearing materials, in time, can lead to failure of the dies through wear, thermal fatigue, mechanical fatigue and plastic deformation (Grote, 2009). If the lubricant breaks down under high pressure, the heat generated due to friction can cause micro-welds to form between the sliding surfaces. This may damage the surface of either the die or bearing.

Figure 12. Normal distribution of bearing sleeve volume

3.3 Forming Load

As part of this analysis, the forming load data was collected from the press machine for later use with model validation (Figure 13). The data was processed in the standard way, using the linear rectification method (Booker et al., 2001). An appropriate curve was then fitted through the statistical data points. The experimental data curve is a regression fit, named the reciprocal logarithm, from the exponential family of numerical models. The curve fit has a strong correlation coefficient (0.996), ensuring a good correlation with the experimental data. Abaqus was used to perform finite-element (FE) analysis on the bearing, using a 3D model with the explicit analysis module. The dies, inner race, outer race and composite liner were all modelled as

individual parts in a CAD package, to ensure precise reconstruction of geometry using data collected from the experimental analysis. The parts were then exported into Abaqus CAE for numerical analysis. Firstly, the global friction coefficient of the models was tuned using bearing parts modelled with mid-tolerance dimensions, as per company engineering drawings. Simulations were run using these parts, with friction coefficients ranging from 0.05μ to 0.45μ . As the FE forming load curve for 0.15μ displayed the highest correlation to the final forming load of the experimental curve, this value was calibrated as the input parameter for the coefficient of friction for future simulations. In reality the friction coefficient changes markedly with pressure (Cora et al., 2008).

Figure 13. Load-displacement graph for nosing

3.4 Frictional Moment

The measured bearings were tracked through the frictional moment adjustment process, whereby each bearing is fine-tuned to the correct frictional moment (the torque required to overcome sticking friction and rotate the bearing outer race around its natural axis). Each bearing sample was tagged to ensure traceability, including through washing and drying processes, and the frictional moment recorded at each stage. Due to the ‘stick-slip’ nature of plain bearings, a single value for frictional moment is challenging to obtain. The average values for frictional moment in the first and last stages are displayed in Figure 14. It can be seen that the first stage post-nosing are best described using a 2-parameter Weibull distribution, as the values are skewed from a zero threshold; whereas, recorded values in the last stage, after they have been adjusted, are near-Normal.

Figure 14. Bearing frictional moment distributions post-nosing and at final inspection

Adhesive bleed-out caused sample 14 to experience the “sticking” failure mode (Figure 3), and produced one of the highest frictional moments consistently throughout the adjustment process. Empirical evidence suggests that this sample had some of the highest values for chamfer geometric concentricity, and difference in chamfer length between either sides of the bearing. Sample 14 also had the most extreme difference in chamfer angles between either sides of the bearing. This will affect the interaction between the dies and bearing sleeve, as the point(s) of contact differ between the upper and lower dies. The stress will increase at any point-contact around the circumference, and may contribute to the variation in forming load at the beginning of the nosing process. An imbalance may even be large enough to produce one of the in-process failure modes outlined in Figure 3, specifically the ‘tipping’ failure. Conversely, sample 2 produced one of the lowest frictional moments throughout the adjustment process. Empirical evidence also indicates that this sample had some of the lowest values for chamfer geometric concentricity, and difference in angle and length between bearing sides.

3.5 Process Capability Data

There is no definitive answer as to exactly how ‘capable’ a feature is (Kotz & Lovelace 1998). Generally, capability targets specify that $C_{pk} < 1.33$ (30ppm) implies that the process is not capable. A value of between 1.33 and 2.5 implies the process is capable, and a value higher than 2.5 indicates that the high precision is potentially expensive. Results from the statistical analysis can be seen in Table 2, and the process capability index of each geometric feature can be compared to that in standard tables for process capability indices (Kotz & Lovelace, 1998).

4. Conclusions

An analysis of geometric tolerances for concentricity, angle and length indicate that the bearing outer race chamfers can be eccentric, with an angular and length disparity between either side. During manufacture, if values of these variables were to fall within the last 5% of the calculated distributions, i.e. a maximum or minimum extreme value, this could easily contribute to the variability within the nosing process. This would be especially true of the start of the process, whereby uniform contact between the dies and outer race is crucial. If tolerances of certain parameters were to be reduced this would reduce the variation in volumetric change between parts. For example, if the minimum/maximum tolerances for chamfer angle, outer chamfer length (axial) and sleeve length were set to 14/16°, 1.2/1.3mm and 26.0/26.1mm respectively, this would reduce the percentage volumetric change to $\pm 0.7\%$. Ideally an increase in the C_{pk} value may reduce variability within the nosing process, however, an increase in the C_p value would still be beneficial in order to reduce batch-to-batch variability. An increase in process capability indices for some features may not be the only solution to reducing variation in the nosing process though.

Table 2. Process capability data for measured features and conformance levels

Variable	Mean (μ)	Standard Deviation (σ)	Tolerance		C_p Index	C_{pk} Index	Parts Non- conforming (ppm)
			LSL	USL			
Concentricity (mm)	0.01	0.02	0	0.06	1.3	1.0	1641
Geometric Concentricity (mm)	0.05	0.19	0	0.06	0.1	0.03	-
Angle (°)	14.45	0.48	13	17	1.4	1.0	1183
Length (mm)	1.20	0.09	1.17	1.46	0.5	0.1	617,912

Consideration must be given to geometric tolerances if the outputs of the nosing process are to be better controlled. Samples 2 and 14 displayed some of the smallest and largest geometric concentricity values, as well as comparably low and high forming loads respectively. Similar behaviour was observed throughout the frictional moment adjustment process. This evidence

indicates that extreme variations in the values of geometric features, especially a large disparity between either side of the bearing outer race, negatively impacts on forming load. Therefore, in order to ensure that the process is more robust, it is recommended to the collaborating company that geometric tolerances be introduced on part drawings. The usual target of $C_{pk} = 1.33$ for the machining process reflects a geometrical tolerance for concentricity of $\pm 10\mu\text{m}$ (Booker et al., 2001) for this sized chamfer, far below that currently achieved, strengthening the case for a process change. Future work includes sensitivity analysis of these geometric features using FE modelling which may indicate which features should be assigned new geometric tolerances as a priority and a cost benefit analysis of the changes.

Acknowledgments

The authors kindly thank the sponsoring company for providing the opportunity and support required to perform this study.

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